

Robust Sonar Image Descriptors for Underwater Place Recognition Trained in Synthetic Scenarios

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Abstract—Underwater Place Recognition presents intricate challenges. These challenges primarily arise from factors such as light absorption and water turbidity, which limit the effectiveness of optical sensors. To circumvent these limitations, sonar systems have emerged as a popular choice for perception in underwater operations. Unlike traditional computer vision algorithms, which often struggle with sonar-generated acoustic images, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) prove more proficient. However, they typically require large labeled training datasets, which are usually difficult to obtain in real-world settings. In light of these constraints, we introduce a compact deep sonar descriptor pipeline. This pipeline is designed for robust generalization to real-world scenarios while exclusively trained on synthetic data. Our architecture combines a ResNet18 back-end with a finely tuned random Gaussian projection layer. We present a tailored procedure for synthetic data generation. Additionally, we employ standard ad-hoc normalization/prefiltering techniques to enhance input sonar data. The proposed method has been evaluated extensively using both synthetic and real public datasets. Our model demonstrates its effectiveness compared to state-of-the-art methods.

Index Terms—Sonar Imaging, Underwater Robotics, Place Recognition.

I. INTRODUCTION

Autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs) are essential for performing intricate tasks in underwater environments, such as exploration, assembly, and maintenance of underwater infrastructure. The autonomous navigation capabilities of AUVs have resulted in economic, environmental, and safety benefits by reducing the necessity for remote piloting and support vessels. Specifically, underwater place recognition is the cornerstone of autonomous navigation capabilities.

However, underwater place recognition faces challenges due to factors like light absorption and water turbidity, hindering optical sensors like RGB cameras. Sonar systems are the preferred choice for underwater perception due to their immunity to these limitations. However, due to the imaging principle of sonar acoustic pulse, the generated sonar image is easily affected by noise. Due to the laborious preprocessing work required, the use of traditional computer vision methods based on feature descriptors is constrained. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs), owing to their exceptional feature extraction capability, have gradually become the primary paradigm for

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Fig. 1: The triplet loss training is used to learn a descriptor that makes similar images spatially close (e.g., top and middle images) and different images spatially distant.

addressing underwater place recognition tasks based on sonar images. [1] first introduced a CNN architecture for predicting similarity scores of underwater sonar images. Subsequently, the triplet loss function [2] [4] was combined with CNNs to learn the latent metric space of synthesized forward sonar images, achieving a more accurate and robust underwater place recognition. Our sonar image descriptors are built on this approach. A significant contribution of our paper is that proposed sonar image descriptors leverage synthetic data to achieve accurate results and substantial overhead savings. Assisted with triplet loss function during training, the network learns the more discriminative feature representation, improving generalization and reducing the risk of overfitting. Experiments show that our sonar image descriptors are able to recognize underwater places efficiently and robustly. In particular, results that are better than state-of-the-art have been obtained on widely used real datasets.

II. METHODS

Acquiring and annotating a large volume of sonar images for training and evaluating deep learning models is both expensive and time-consuming. Therefore, the simulated en-

Fig. 2: Architecture of the descriptors extraction network. The features extracted from ResNet18 are converted to 128-dimensional image descriptors using Random Gaussian Projection (RGP) and afterward downsampled to unit length.

environment proposed in [3] and Gazebo simulator¹ are utilized to synthesize training data. In the simulation environment, sonar parameters can be freely controlled, and ground truth pose information can be easily retrieved. Eventually, a dataset encompassing three objects was collected for training the network. The complete training dataset comprises approximately 5,000 sonar images, with 20% of the images used as anchor points. It should be remarked that in order to properly assess the generalization ability of the proposed method, the geometry of the objects we used in the simulation environment is significantly different from the ones in the public dataset used in the final experiments.

As shown in Fig. 2, the backbone of our model is a modified ResNet18 encoder network capable of accepting single-channel input. The input of the network consists of raw sonar images (beams×bins), resized to 256×200 dimensions. Gaussian Random Projection (RGP) is leveraged to reduce the size of descriptors to 128 dimensions. Finally, descriptors are normalized to unit length.

We can see clearly from Fig. 1 that the training process is controlled by the triplet loss function. The triple loss requires that the training samples be classified as either positive or negative samples with respect to any given anchor point. To achieve this, we adopt a similarity metric strategy proposed in [4], where the similarity between two sonar scans is defined as the relative overlap area between their respective sonar Field-of-VIEWS (FOVs). Setting a similarity threshold governs the division of positive and negative samples. In contrast to prior work [4], we introduce three innovations: i) Using cosine distance instead of Euclidean distance in the triplet loss; ii) Replacing the final fully connected layer with a fixed RGP matrix (resulting in reduced trainable parameters); iii) Focusing on forward-looking sonar rather than side-scan sonar.

Notably, a further contribution we introduce is a customized sonar image enhancement scheme to reduce noise interference. In the first step, the sonar insonification pattern is obtained by averaging a large number of images in the same dataset, and the resulting pattern is used to normalize pixel intensities. Then, discrete wavelet transformation(DWT) is employed to filter images. Finally, the Constant False Alarm Rate (CFAR) thresholding technique is used to obtain binary images.

¹<https://gazebosim.org/home>

TABLE I: Comparison of underwater place recognition performance on Aracati2014 dataset

Method	AUC	P	R	R@95
Random	.85	.94	.93	.78
NetVLAD	.83	.92	.92	.14
Ours	.86	.95	.95	.93

TABLE II: Comparison of underwater place recognition performance on Aracati2017 dataset

Method	AUC	P	R	R@95
Random	.91	.99	.99	.99
NetVLAD	.68	.95	.94	.00
Ours	.75	.99	.99	.99

III. RESULTS

We evaluate our sonar image descriptors on the publicly available Aracati2014 and Aracati2017 datasets. The classical F1-Score is adopted as the evaluation metric. In response to the requirements of loop closure detection in simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) for place recognition, we novelty introduce a metric, Recall at 95% precision (R@95). In Table I and Table II, we compare our method with the state-of-the-art NetVLAD and model with randomly initialized weights. The results show the effectiveness and excellent generalization ability of our descriptors. Note that our descriptor significantly outperforms the state-of-the-art model NetVLAD with satisfactory results.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we propose robust sonar image descriptors that are trained by synthesizing data. Descriptors are used for underwater place localization while obtaining better results than state of the arts on real datasets. We also provide improved triple-loss training strategies, customized image enhancement schemes, and innovative evaluation strategies. In the future, more advanced sonar simulators will also be employed to synthesize higher-quality training data.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. O. C. S. Ribeiro, M. M. dos Santos, P. L. J. Drews and S. S. C. Botelho, "Forward Looking Sonar Scene Matching Using Deep Learning," 2017 16th IEEE International Conference on Machine Learning and Applications (ICMLA), Cancun, Mexico, 2017, pp. 574-579.
- [2] P. O. C. S. Ribeiro et al., "Underwater Place Recognition in Unknown Environments with Triplet Based Acoustic Image Retrieval," 2018 17th IEEE International Conference on Machine Learning and Applications (ICMLA), Orlando, FL, USA, 2018, pp. 524-529.
- [3] M. M. Zhang et al., "DAVE Aquatic Virtual Environment: Toward a General Underwater Robotics Simulator," 2022 IEEE/OES Autonomous Underwater Vehicles Symposium (AUV), Singapore, 2022, pp. 1-8.
- [4] M. Larsson, N. Bore and J. Folkesson, "Latent Space Metric Learning For Sidescan Sonar Place Recognition," 2020 IEEE/OES Autonomous Underwater Vehicles Symposium (AUV), St. Johns, NL, Canada, 2020, pp. 1-6.